

Country Dossier Poland

WP7: Return Aspirations and Trajectories of Migrants

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Summary

The report presents findings on migration trajectories of various categories of migrants in Poland. The research focused on return as a result of a given person's experience and aspirations. The primary data were obtained through qualitative analysis of 31 individual in-depth interviews with migrants. The study draws on a critical approach to migration, assuming a continuum of coercion in different types of returns. It assumes that coercion varies depending on the personal situation of each migrant and the way state institutions apply policy. It is not necessarily reflected straightforwardly by the name of a legal category of return, such as 'voluntary' returns. The report starts with laying down the context of migration to Poland in terms of policies and their application.

The people interviewed for the study belonged to various, sometimes overlapping groups:

- migrants at risk of return, including irregular migrants (e.g., those with a expired stay permit),
- individuals who experienced pushbacks at the border with Belarus,
- migrants who were denied entry or rejected for asylum in the EU,
- migrants with removal orders, those briefly detained, and returnees who re-entered Poland,
- migrants returning from or to Poland within the Dublin procedures,
- voluntary returnees (as classified by IOM) to highlight the complexities beyond the forced/voluntary binary.

In the report, four categories of trajectories are identified and developed, taking into account agency in the very act of migration, the experience of integration, and the plans and aspirations concerning return or further mobility. The following categories are differentiated: 'planning settlers', 'planning nomads', 'spontaneous settlers', and 'spontaneous nomads'. In conclusion, the report underlines that migrants exercise their agency even in situations usually perceived as 'forced migration', and this agency should be recognised and adequately depicted. Moreover, eleven policy recommendations are proposed.

Keywords: migration trajectories, returns, deportation, pushbacks, integration

GAPs Project and WP7

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of ‘return policymaking’. To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance,
- analyses enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures,
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return, and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary three-year project (March 2023–February 2026), co-coordinated by the Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs’ fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Afghanistan, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Poland, Sweden, Tunisia, and Turkey.

WP7 investigates migrants’ experiences of return or remaining at risk of return, emphasising how they navigate their return decisions within broader (im)mobility experiences. The research employs a multilevel lens, examining personal experiences, the role of diaspora organisations, and the effects of state policies on migration trajectories. Conducted through anthropological and sociological methodologies across Turkey, Greece, Poland, Morocco, and additional interviews in Sweden and Germany, the study seeks to enhance understanding of migrant agency and contribute to the development of effective and humane migration policies.

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1. Introduction

This report investigates migrants' experiences in Poland, considered both a transit and a destination country (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2022) during both the post- and the pre-return phases (who experienced return and/or are at risk of thereof), examining how they consider, decide, and communicate their return decisions within broader (im)mobility experiences. It aims to enhance understanding of migrant agency and offers a micro-analytical perspective. It also explores how return and readmission policies affect migrants' rights and living conditions, taking into account our diverse interviewee sample regarding the country of origin and legal status.

The broader objective of the report is to model return trajectories, highlighting how onward movements, re-orientations, rest periods, and intermediate settlements develop. It also aims to identify the influence of diaspora organisations and transnational networks on migration trajectories and returns. Another key focus is on exploring migrant agency, particularly how states of 'limbo' or 'liminality' impact trajectories, and how their agency should be reflected in projecting return policies.

Led by Özyeğin University (OzU) and AMI in Turkey and Morocco, respectively, with support from SRII in Turkey, EKKE in Greece, and the University of Warsaw (UW) in Poland, WP7 employs anthropological and sociological methods to study prospective returnees. This includes both regular and irregular migrants, those in voluntary return programmes, and individuals facing forced return, as well as those who have already returned and can reflect on their experiences.

The project examines return trajectories through a multilevel lens:

1. **Micro Level:** Focuses on personal experiences, including how social contexts, networks, and media influence decision-making. Factors like labour market integration, personal connections, and local or transnational media play a role. Particular emphasis is placed on gender dynamics in deciding and planning return, along with past return attempts and encounters with pushbacks or return infrastructures linked to the EU.
2. **Meso Level:** Examines the role of actors such as diaspora and migrant organisations in shaping trajectories, utilising contextual knowledge and connections.
3. **Macro Level:** Analyses how policies impact trajectories, either encouraging or inhibiting return and reinforcing settlement patterns.

This comprehensive approach seeks to illuminate the complexities of migrant experiences and contribute to more effective, humane migration policies.

2. Methods

This study employed a combination of anthropological and sociological fieldwork methods to examine migration dynamics among prospective returnees. The research adopted a multilevel perspective, analysing migrant trajectories with a focus on changing aspirations, social embeddedness, and mobility decisions. The report uses the term 'migrant' as encompassing people with different experiences and statuses, including asylum-seekers. The term 'return'

means mobility back to the previous destination (mainly but not necessarily the country of origin) with a range of coercion: varying from high in the case of pushbacks and forced removals, to low—but still entailing coercion—regarding voluntary returns¹.

At the micro level, the study explored the influence of personal experiences on return decisions, encompassing the feelings, insights from family and friend networks, information from local or transnational media, and the migrant's labour market position and integration experiences in the host or transit country. The research also examined past return attempts (both voluntary and forced), experiences with pushbacks, and interactions with readmission and return systems (in Poland and other countries), particularly in relation to the EU, assessing the impact of risks on individual return trajectories.

Preparation for fieldwork included team discussions on qualitative research practices, interviewing techniques, and ethical considerations. Researchers utilised a WP7 Conceptual Framework and Interview Guideline, structured to facilitate mapping migrant trajectories and examining agency, governance, networks, and integration contexts. The guideline provided four primary questions with optional sub-questions, ensuring a clear focus while allowing flexibility in the interviews. The interviews were conducted in line with the university requirements and were preceded by obtaining clearance from the Ethics Committee of the Centre of Migration Research at the University of Warsaw. The principles of informed consent and anonymous participation were crucial for the research team when conducting the interviews. The respondents were informed about the project's scope and aim of the research activities. Interviews were conducted with participant consent, with measures for anonymity and the option for participants to skip questions or end the interview at any time. Where permission was granted, interviews were audio-recorded and securely stored.

Recruitment of participants was flexible in terms of dates, locations, and nationalities, specifically targeting individuals who have already experienced return and/or are at risk of return (with various levels of coercion), including irregular migrants, those with removal orders, and asylum-seekers. Recruitment strategies involved partnerships with organisations, researchers' contacts, and fieldworkers' pre-existing connections. Interviews lasted, on average, several minutes to several tens of minutes, but no longer than an hour. The degree of openness of the interviewees varied depending on their legal situation. Ethical considerations included maintaining anonymity and omitting sensitive questions as needed. The psychological aspects of the research were considered according to the most up-to-date scholarship on this issue (Radziwinowiczówna 2024). The team discussed the possibility of re-traumatisation of the interviewees and prepared the information about the access to free psychological counselling provided in different languages. Interviews were conducted in English, Russian, Polish, Turkish, and Hindi. The collected data were transcribed, coded, and analysed.

In Poland, we approached more than 50 potential interviewees in 2024. Some of them initially agreed to be interviewed but eventually opted out or avoided contact. This can be explained for various reasons, such as waiting for decisions in different proceedings or they had left

¹ We acknowledge that in some cases so-called 'voluntary' returns may be, in fact, forced to some degree by pressure from the uniformed services or procedural arrangements.

Poland. In total, 31 micro-level interviews were conducted with the following participant categories (these are intersectional) (see Table 1):

- migrants at risk of return, including irregular migrants (e.g., those with a expired stay permit),
- individuals who experienced pushbacks at the border with Belarus,
- migrants who were denied entry or rejected for asylum in the EU,
- migrants with removal orders, those briefly detained, and returnees who re-entered Poland,
- migrants returning from or to Poland within the Dublin procedures,
- voluntary returnees (as classified by IOM) to highlight the complexities beyond the forced/voluntary binary.

These categories reflect the specific conditions in Poland regarding return and deportation, aiming to capture a diverse range of at-risk populations. Legal status and nationality were not the sole criteria, as many migrants without permanent residence or citizenship in Poland face heightened vulnerability. Sampling focused on at-risk individuals, prioritising socio-demographic diversity within and across groups, though limited interview numbers reduced representativity.

Table 1 Interview participants

No.	Interview code	Age range	Gender	Country of origin	Legal status	Working currently
1	WP7_1	31-50	Male	Pakistan	Without legal stay	Yes
2	WP7_2	18-30	Male	Morocco	Returned	Yes
3	WP7_3	18-30	Male	Rwanda	Temporary permit of stay	Studying
4	WP7_4	18-30	Male	Turkey	Temporary permit of stay	Yes
5	WP7_5	18-30	Male	Palestine/Lebanon	Asylum	Studying
6	WP7_6	31-50	Male	Russia (Chechen ethnicity)	Asylum seeker	No
7	WP7_7	31-50	Male	Russia (Chechen ethnicity)	Permanent permit of stay	Yes
8	WP7_8	18-30	Male	India	Voluntary return from Poland to Latvia	Studying
9	WP7_9	18-30	Male	Iraq	Asylum in Germany	Studying
10	WP7_10	50+	Female	Ukraine	Without legal stay	Yes
11	WP7_11	18-30	Male	Iran	Asylum	Yes

12	WP7_12	50+	Male	Iran	Returned forcibly	Yes
13	WP7_13	31-50	Male	Bangladesh	Temporary permit of stay	Yes
14	WP7_14	18-30	Male	Afghanistan	Asylum in Germany	Yes
15	WP7_15	31-50	Male	Tajikistan	Asylum seeker	No
16	WP7_16	31-50	Male	Tajikistan	Asylum in Italy	No
17	WP7_17	31-50	Female	Russia (Dagestan)	Asylum seeker in Germany	No
18	WP7_18	18-30	Male	Sudan	Asylum seeker	No
19	WP7_19	18-30	Male	Eritrea	Asylum seeker	No
20	WP7_20	18-30	Male	Sudan	Asylum seeker	No
21	WP7_21	50+	Male	Russia	Asylum seeker	No
22	WP7_22	31-50	Female	Russia (Chechen ethnicity)	Returned forcibly	No
23	WP7_23	31-50	Female	Turkey (Kurdish ethnicity)	Returned forcibly	No
24	WP7_24	18-30	Male	India	Asylum seeker	No
25	WP7_25	31-50	Female	Russia (Chechen ethnicity)	Asylum	Yes
26	WP7_26	18-30	Male	Sri Lanka	Without legal stay	Yes
27	WP7_27	18-30	Trans Male	Uzbekistan	Without legal stay	Yes
28	WP7_28	50+	Female	Ukraine	Temporary protection	No
29	WP7_29	31-50	Female	Ukraine	Temporary protection	No
30	WP7_30	31-50	Female	Ukraine	Temporary protection	No
31	WP7_31	31-50	Male	Azerbaijan	Temporary permit of stay	Yes

Source: Own elaboration.

Sampling criteria

Nationality and Legal Status: Risk or experience of deportation was a primary focus among sampling criteria for micro-level interview participants. Therefore, the sample does not reflect the demographic characteristics and structure of the migrant population in Poland. Ukrainians, vastly the biggest group among the total foreign population, due to the temporary protection scheme in force since February 2022, do not remain at the highest risk of return (at least until the Temporary Protection is in force which is now until 30 September 2025 in Poland and until 4 March 2026 in the EU).

The sample aimed to reflect the ethnic diversity among people who predominantly face practices of Poland's return system². However, it has to be noted that during the research, a significant challenge was linked to accessing the main nationalities for whom the orders to leave were issued: Georgians, Belarussians, and Moldovans in particular. While the ratio of Belarussians ordered to leave to those holding residence permits remains extremely low (around 1%), for Georgians and Moldovans, it is considerable (approx. 11% and 12.5%, respectively, drawing on the data of the Office for Foreigners, see Figure 1). This limitation should be taken into account. The difficulty in reaching Georgians and Moldovans could result from the relatively high occurrence of criminal reasons for removals concerning citizens of these countries, which can lead to a lack of willingness among these groups to participate in a study. According to the data obtained on 22 January 2025 from the Police (through access to public information) there were 2,655 and 2,714 Georgians suspected of a crime in 2022 and 2023, respectively (582 and 784 Moldovans, respectively). Compared to the number of residence permit holders, the ratio of suspected persons in 2022 was 13.7% among Georgians and 8.5% among Moldovans, while only 2% among Ukrainians and 1.5% among Belarussians.

Particular attention was paid to the migrants entering Poland in the context of instrumentalised migration by Belarus, described by both governments³ as a 'hybrid attack'⁴, which results in the possibility of being pushed back at the Polish-Belarussian border. Seven people from the sample crossed the border in this way, and the highest ethical sensitivity was ensured while conducting the interviews with them.

The following figures present the main statistical data on the migrant population in Poland regarding returns. Figure 1 depicts international protection applications in Poland in 2023. The final negative decision (after a possible appeal) regarding protection results in the obligation to leave Poland within 30 days.

² For more about Poland's return system, see (Trylińska et al. 2024).

³ This applies to the right-wing coalition government of Law and Justice (2015-2023) and the new broad coalition government formed in late 2023 led by Civic Coalition.

⁴ See more in the section *Researching returns in the context of the crisis on the border with Belarus and displacement from Ukraine*.

Figure 1 Five of the top 10 nationalities applying for international protection in Poland in 2023

Source: The Office for Foreigners. <https://www.gov.pl/web/udsc/zestawienia-roczne> (last accessed 5 November 2024).

Figure 2 presents issued orders to leave Poland in 2023, including the category of refused asylum-seekers and all other removals issued on different grounds⁵. Figure 3 concerns the situation on the border with Belarus. While the proper data on the number of people crossing this border and experiencing pushbacks are not available, there are sources presented by NGOs on the number of people who requested different kinds of assistance (humanitarian, medical, legal) after crossing the border. This group remains at a high risk of return in the form of pushbacks. Some of them, however, become asylum-seekers after their asylum applications are accepted to be lodged by the Border Guard (see more in the section *Researching returns in the context of the crisis on the border with Belarus and displacement from Ukraine*).

⁵ For more on the legal framework concerning returns, see (Trylińska et al. 2024).

Figure 2 Orders to leave by nationality in Poland in 2023

Source: The Office for Foreigners. <https://www.gov.pl/web/udsc/zestawienia-roczne> (last accessed 5 November 2024).

Figure 3 Top five nationalities who requested humanitarian assistance in Poland on the border with Belarus since 16.06.2022

Source: We Are Monitoring. <https://wearemonitoring.org.pl/en/home/?cn-reloaded=1> (last accessed 5 November 2024).

Finally, Figure 4 presents the population of migrants holding a residence permit, both labour migrants and beneficiaries of international protection (this does not include the beneficiaries of Temporary Protection). The situation of labour migrants is dependent on their

employment contract, which means that they may face the necessity to return if they lose their job and cannot find another one or if they skip the deadline for the prolongation of their residence permit, which is issued for three years at the longest.

Figure 4 Top five nationalities holding residence permits in Poland on 1 January 2024

Source: The Office for Foreigners. <https://www.gov.pl/web/udsc/zestawienia-roczne> (last accessed 5 November 2024).

Socio-Demographic Factors: There are insufficient publicly available data disaggregated by the gender of persons in return proceedings or pushed back. Residual data is available, e.g., in some reports and datasets provided by NGOs such as the Association ‘We Are Monitoring’, which is part of the Border Group coalition⁶. In our sample, women constitute only 26%. The dominance of men in the sample results from the prevalence of them among irregular migrants and asylum-seekers (especially on the border with Belarus).

The dominant age range of our interviewees is 18-30 (14 people) followed by 31-50 (13 people). The remaining four are people over 50 years-old. The sample is almost equally divided concerning the occupational status: 17 people work or study while 14 do not have any current occupation, while the majority have higher education.

There is no strong majority of a given family situation, with both single people and those living as a couple represented. The same applies to those having obligations towards children or parents and those not providing care for any family member.

⁶ See the data and reports available on the website: <https://wearemonitoring.org.pl/en/home/>.

Data collection locations

Interviews were conducted with people staying in Poland in different cities (including Warsaw, Lublin, Cracow, and open reception centres) as well as with people who are abroad either in Western Europe or in their countries of origin or destination. The interviews with people staying abroad were conducted online, while with those living in Poland, both online and on-site. People not remaining in Poland were included in the sample to obtain knowledge about their experience of return and regarding possible re-emigration.

3. Context

Brief description of the migration and return governance system (2015–2023)⁷

In the early 1990s, Poland joined the international system of human rights protection, which also applies to the issue of return migration: the Geneva Convention relating to the Status of Refugees of 1951, the Council of Europe (in both cases, it was 1991), and the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950 (in 1993) (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2022, pp. 20-40). Other important changes were linked to the accession to the EU, however, according to some scholars, this process was rather superficial, forced by the need to adapt the law to EU requirements, and not based on experience and values (Weinar 2006; Łazor 2016). In any case, adopting both the international and the EU-based legal framework was a crucial political factor shaping the emergence of the return system in post-transition Poland.

Until the so-called migration-management crisis in 2015, migration policy occupied a rather marginal position compared to other public policies in Poland⁸. Between 1990 and 2015, Poland was primarily an emigration country, and immigration was mainly dealt with technocratically and administratively (Matyja, Siewierska-Chmaj, Pędziwiatr 2015; Adamczyk 2021). Return policy was not in the spotlight and some efforts were even made to decrease the need to apply returns, like three abolitions allowing migrants to regularise their status that took place in 2003, 2007/08, and 2012⁹.

Since 2015, migration has remained a highly securitised topic in Poland (Adamczyk 2017), strengthening the urge to apply returns effectively. The government formed by the Law and Justice (PiS) party in 2015-2023 based its rhetoric on anti-immigrant sentiment (Fomina, Kucharczyk 2018; Górak-Sosnowska, Pachocka, 2019; Klaus 2020). In 2016, the PiS government abolished the previous government's migration policy strategy, which had been adopted in 2012. It also refused to participate in the EU temporary relocation scheme from Italy and Greece, which provoked a clash with the EU institutions (Pachocka 2016; Pachocka et Caballero-Vélez 2025). The anti-immigrant policy was especially visible in the case of providing protection to foreigners in the territory of Poland, with reported refusals of access to asylum at the border crossing with Belarus in Terespol shortly after PiS took power in 2015

⁷ For more details, see Section 2. Political Context (Trylińska et al. 2024, pp. 15-16).

⁸ With the exception of the return migration of Poles.

⁹ The number of applications was about 5,500, 2,050, and 8,800, respectively. With the last amnesty, most of the applicants received positive decisions and the main countries of origin were Ukraine, Vietnam, and Armenia (Infor.pl 2012).

(Szczepanik 2018). The situation was exacerbated in 2021 when Belarusian dictator Alexander Lukashenka instrumentalised migration, mostly from the Middle East and Africa, to facilitate or even force irregular border crossings to Poland, Latvia, and Lithuania. This resulted in systemic violence against migrants, militarisation of the border regime, and pushbacks (Krępa 2022; WAM 2024; Krępa, Fernández de la Reguera 2024; Bronitskaya et al. 2024). Even with pushbacks, however, some international protection applications were allowed to be lodged, and after rejection, the number of returns increased considerably. Importantly, the change of government in autumn 2023 has not seemed to alter the situation considerably so far (Krępa et al. 2024).

The situation regarding labour migration was different. Due to significant labour market shortages and pressure from employers, the migration policy of PiS was shaped rather by economic logic and remained liberal despite the securitisation within the border and asylum regimes (Jaroszewicz, Krępa and Pachocka 2024). Importantly, most of the labour migrants come from countries that were not the object of securitisation in the Polish discourse on migration, predominantly Ukraine (Jaroszewicz, Grzymiski 2021). Moreover, the so-called ‘visa scandal’ exposed that the procedures for granting visas were faulty and that many foreigners obtained visas to Poland improperly.

Another important development shaping the migration system in Poland was the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022. Poland followed the EU legal framework from the Council Directive 2001/55/EC of 20 July 2001 on minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof. It was activated by the Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382 of 4 March 2022 establishing the existence of a mass influx of displaced persons from Ukraine within the meaning of Article 5 of Directive 2001/55/EC and having the effect of introducing temporary protection. Poland has even gone a step further by adopting the Law of 12 March 2022 on assistance to citizens of Ukraine in connection with armed conflict on the territory of the country. The general policy towards people fleeing the war was rather open-door based (Pachocka 2022; Jaroszewicz, Grzymiski, Krępa 2022). However, the question of further stay of Ukrainian beneficiaries of temporary protection in Poland may become an essential issue regarding the return policy depending on the war-related developments in the near future. The same applies to the temporary character of this protection, which was several times prolonged; however, there is always a risk that prolongation in the next year will not occur.

Researching returns in the context of the crisis on the border with Belarus and displacement from Ukraine

Poland’s migration system has been considerably impacted by two geopolitical factors: Belarus’s instrumentalisation of migration (since 2021) and the full-scale Russian aggression in Ukraine (since 2022). The Polish government’s policies in response to these phenomena shape migrants’ mobility possibilities and trajectories, as signalled above. In this section, however, a look at migrants’ perspectives is provided. The policies based on deterrence of migrants on the border with Belarus impact considerably the way in which returns in this context can be researched, especially in terms of interviewing these migrants themselves. In

turn, the special solutions provided for Ukrainians after the full-scale Russian invasion make them the biggest group of migrants in Poland, however, with considerably low risk of deportation.

The situation on the border with Belarus is an effect of the instrumentalisation of migration by the Belarusian government. This process involves the cooperation of the Belarusian authorities with travel agencies and airlines facilitating travel to the territory of this country. The migrants then either cross the border irregularly to reach a country other than Poland, or do so with the intention of applying for international protection. This situation has been taking place since the summer of 2021 and the construction of a 'wall' (fortified border) has not stopped the process (WAM 2024). Returns on the border with Belarus are performed mainly in the form of pushbacks, i.e., the immediate forced return of a person away from the border crossing and without the cooperation of the services of Belarus (WAM 2024; Bronitskaya et al. 2024).

As scholars note, the humanitarian crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border is a situation providing extremely limited possibilities for the migrants themselves to express their stories and experiences in public (Krępa, Mondal 2023). Therefore, there is a scarcity of research based on their testimonies. This is reinforced by the fact that it would not be ethical to conduct studies in the borderland forests with people whose lives are endangered. It should be noted that, in general, doing research with people whose legal status is undetermined and who are hiding and relying on support and legal assistance is problematic. Some studies have already been published, based on the migrants' communication with assistance phones run by the NGO 'Ocalenie' Foundation (Pałęcka 2022), but the voices of such migrants are mostly conveyed by NGOs or journalists in the form of reports and press interviews (see, e.g., WAM 2024; Bronitskaya et al. 2024). The main forms of communication of migrants crossing the border from Belarus to Poland with a general audience can be categorised into five types (Krępa, Mondal 2023). These are short messages such as 'I want asylum in Poland', displayed when encountering the Border Guards, press interviews, official letters written in detention centres, communication with the assistance phone (partly published in Pałęcka 2022), and artistic actions. Each form provides migrants with a different scope of agency and shapes their possibilities for unlimited expression in various ways. As the quoted authors note, the majority of the migrants on the border who face pushbacks, in fact, speak but are mostly unheard, as they do not possess real opportunities to produce their own effective discourse, contrary to the asylum-seekers in open reception centres or regularised migrants as they cannot participate in a demonstration or write a blog, for example.

This study makes an ethical effort to break this silence. None of the interviews were conducted in the forest while the migrants remained in highly vulnerable situations. Instead, seven interviews were conducted with people who crossed the border from Belarus when they were in a relatively safe place: in the open reception centre as registered asylum-seekers awaiting a decision or when they were already farther abroad in Western Europe. These people had either faced pushbacks or were at risk of them.

Quite a different situation is linked to the displacement from Ukraine, which is the corollary of the full-scale Russian aggression against this country since 24 February 2022. As already depicted, this group of migrants was provided with relatively unlimited access to Poland's territory, as well as with the inclusion into the social security system and labour market (Act of 2022). Although Ukrainians form the vast majority of the migrant population in Poland

(before the Russian invasion but also after it, in particular), they remain at quite low risk of deportation due to the temporary protection scheme and the ongoing war on Ukrainian territory. However, at the same time, it would be wrong to perceive this war-related migration as occurring only in one direction. Even in the first months after the invasion, 6.8 million Ukrainians and foreigners staying in Ukraine left their country, while 2.3 million Ukrainian citizens returned to Ukraine (these numbers consider mobility between Ukraine and all other countries as of the end of May 2022; UNHCR, quoted in Duszczyk, Kaczmarczyk 2022a). This number includes *inter alia* men who decided to enrol to the army or territorial defence formations (Duszczyk, Kaczmarczyk 2022b). As Gluszak and Trojanek (2024, p. 16) argue, based on a literature review, ‘since August 2022, Poland has witnessed an exodus of Ukrainians who either migrated to other European countries (mainly Germany) or returned to their homes in Ukraine’. Many Ukrainians return to Ukraine due to the difficulties in supporting themselves as the social support in host countries is shrinking—this is particularly observed among the vulnerable displaced groups like Ukrainian Roma (Rozanova 2024). As a result, the number of Ukrainians registered in Poland’s temporary protection scheme decreased from 1.5 million at the beginning of 2023 to about 950 thousand by the end of this year (The Republic of Poland’s Open Data Platform n.d.; UNHCR n.d.; Dziennik Gazeta Prawna 2023; TVN24 2024).

Thus, while Ukrainian migration to Poland after the start of the full-scale Russian aggression is linked to numerous returns and re-emigration, it is considerably less targeted by the state return system. This is reflected by the number of orders to leave issued for Ukrainian citizens, which stood at only 475 in 2023 (The Office for Foreigners n.d.) and were mostly based on security reasons or repeated criminal acts¹⁰. It should be remembered, however, that the question remains whether the temporary protection (currently in force until September 2025 in Poland) will be prolonged.

There is an emerging body of scholarship on the situation of beneficiaries of Temporary Protection, including their willingness to return (Kubiciel-Łodzińska et al. 2023; Duszczyk et al. 2023; Gońda 2024) as well as the discourse on ‘real’ refugees from Ukraine (Bloch 2023; Tomczak-Boczko, Gołębiowska, Górny 2023). This is why the situation of this group is relatively well-researched compared to the other groups included in our study.

Social, economic, and political conditions of migrants’ integration and returns

Trajectories of migrants and their plans concerning return are often conditioned by integration prospects, which stem from two factors. The first one, potentially mitigating the willingness to return, is the low unemployment rate (since June 2017, no higher than 7%; GUS 2024) and ease of obtaining and prolonging stay permits based on a labour contract. The latter stems from the strong position of employers, resulting in relatively liberal policies on labour migration (Jaroszewicz, Krępa, Pachocka 2024). The second factor, acting in the opposite way, is a lack of integration measures for labour migrants, as state integration programmes are limited only to beneficiaries of international protection (excluding temporary protection).

¹⁰ There are no official data on the reasons for the orders to leave, but we obtained this information unofficially from an expert in the field.

NGOs carry out significant activities in the domain of the integration of migrants in Poland, and, despite the lack of institutionalised coordination with national or regional authorities, the NGOs often receive public funding (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2020). However, during the Law and Justice government (2015-2023), the public funding for NGOs with the aim to integrate migrants was limited (Mołęda-Zdziech, Pachocka, Wach 2021). Since February 2022, new funding streams were established, including from the UN agencies and INGOs, targeting mostly the Ukrainian refugee population.

Local authorities, including municipalities, gradually started to develop their own migration policies in the absence of such a policy at the central level (Wach, Pachocka 2022; Pachocka et al. 2025). However, as Poland remains a unitary and quite centralised state, this was possible only to a limited extent. Therefore, integration policies remained fragmented and diversified depending on the city and region.

At the same time, the general anti-migrant discourse has been on the rise. Migrants from the Middle East and Africa have been portrayed (by the Law and Justice government and right-wing media in particular) as a threat to Poland's culture, security, and values, which contributed to incidents of racism and discrimination against migrants in general and Muslims in particular, despite the neutral or positive narratives about labour migration (Hargrave, Homel, Dražanová 2023). This was exacerbated by linking Muslim migration with terrorism (Górak-Sosnowska, Pachocka 2019; Mołęda-Zdziech, Pachocka, Wach 2019). Since mid-2021, in the case of the crisis on the border with Belarus, various anti-migrant discourses were developed (Krępa, Judzińska 2023) based on the concept of 'hybrid warfare'¹¹ (Straczuk 2023) and employ gendered and racialised narratives (Bloch 2023). On the contrary, there are relatively easy prospects for the integration of Ukrainians due to cultural proximity, language similarities, and lack of 'physical features perceived as racially different to Poles' (Koss-Goryszewska, Pawlak 2018, p. 182). However, some anti-Ukrainian sentiments are also on the rise (Fomina, Pachocka 2024).

Gender and ethnicity can impact integration prospects. One study found discrimination against Arab men in the Polish housing market (Antfolk, Szala, Öblom 2019). Also, gender was found to be a significant excluding factor in the labour market because migrant women were often responsible for childcare (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2020). At the same time, research proves some level of migrant women's agency in business and entrepreneurship in Poland. For example, Belarusian and Ukrainian women contributed to the development of the beauty sector by establishing a variety of salons (Homel 2022). Also, some NGOs created by migrants are active, especially those run by Ukrainians and Belarusians. After the fraudulent elections in Belarus in 2020, the Belarusian diaspora remains an active political actor in terms of advocacy for its state's democratic opposition (Jaroszewicz, Lesińska, Homel 2022).

In the case of migrants without legal status, limited access to public services or social assistance was observed, together with unclear provisions of the immigration laws, long procedures, and a shortage of qualified staff in public immigration institutions. Furthermore, migrants in Poland can fall into irregularity relatively easily due to the procedural issues

¹¹ This concept, used widely by both the national and EU administrations, refers to instrumentalisation of migration by Belarus. The vagueness of the term, its connotations with military threats, and, consequently, instrumental use by suspending the right to asylum, have been criticised by security scholars (Grabau 2023; Błaszczuk 2023; Krępa 2024).

related to certain situations such as a change of employer (Matuszczyk, Grzymała-Kazłowska, Homel 2024).

4. Migration trajectories regarding plans of return

In analysing migrant trajectories, we focus on their agency and avoid simplistic binaries. This is in line with the underpinnings of the GAPs project, which sees a continuum of coercion of returns rather than strictly separated categories and divisions between ‘forced’ and ‘voluntary’ migration.

As Oliver Bakewell (2010) noted, human agency constitutes a predicament for creating neat theories in social sciences, including migration studies. The model trajectories we present are not a one-size-fits-all label to be attached to migrants, as each bears a unique and individual life story. Instead, they attempt to understand how people gradually exercise agency in two dimensions: planning their mobility and forecasting their return. Importantly, a person can change the trajectory during his or her migration process.

Figure 5 Matrix of migrants’ trajectories

Source: Own elaboration.

In Figure 5, the vertical axis represents the declared level of agency within decision-making to migrate: the further to the top of the axis, the more people were declaring control over their mobility, which means that they meticulously gathered and analysed information about the routes and destinations, conducting a well-thought through selection. The further to the bottom, the more they expressed the feeling that their mobility was a result of an external force or an accident. This regards both people who considered themselves to be forced to move for, e.g., security reasons or who depicted their migration as result of chance, coincidence, a hint,

or an emotional impulse. The horizontal axis mirrors their willingness to go back to the country of origin: the further left on the axis, the more they feel settled where they currently live, while the further right, they are prone to continuous mobility, which means either returning or moving to another country. Importantly, it is impossible to ‘objectively’ measure a person's agency. Rather, we look at how they assess their decisions by themselves, so this is the declared agency of a given person.

Again, we emphasise that the boundaries between the four categories created by the matrix are liquid. We aim to elucidate the agency of migrants, which often remains ignored (Mainwaring 2016; Mainwaring, Walton-Roberts 2018). Hence, we continue the efforts already made in Polish migration studies to see migrants as ‘actors of change’ (Grabowska et al. 2017) by elaborating on the agency of migrants in the most precarious situations. In the literature, this was done in the case of asylum-seekers in terms of their security (Krępa 2021), women in business (Homel 2022), and people who had experienced a pushback as discourse producers (Pałęcka 2022; Krępa, Judzińska 2023; Krępa, Mondal 2023). The offered reflection on trajectories can thus be a starting point for more theoretically informed research on migrants’ agency in Poland in the return domain.

5. Findings

In this section, we present the results of our interviews according to the trajectories mentioned above. The aim of the report is to explore how the concerns about and plans for return are shaped by various factors stemming from the situation of a given person in the country of origin, personal life, travel experience, and integration prospects in the current place of stay. The findings follow the logic of laying down agency in the very act of migration, then moving to the experience of integration, and concluding with the plans and aspirations concerning return or further mobility. We strive for balance, presenting the widest possible context of our interviewees with the principle of ensuring anonymity.

‘Planning settlers’

The trajectory of planning settlers is marked by a high level of declared agency and the tendency to settle permanently in the place where they live currently. Therefore, we do not focus on the reasons for staying but on the overall process of migration and the declared feeling of possessing control over it. This goes beyond the dichotomy of forced/voluntary migrants and, in fact, many planning settlers could be labelled as ‘forced migrants’. However, what is distinctive for them is that despite the mobility triggered often by security reasons, they decided to take as much control as possible over their route, selection of the destination, and possible future of settling down.

Agency in movement

Planning settlers were experiencing high level of agency regarding how they plan their journey and choose the destination. Prior to departure, they were looking for information among people, building up their social networks, and, on the internet, considering many factors such

as the strictness and time for migration procedures, job or education opportunities, and even weather conditions.

One of the people who planned their migration and wanted to settle in Poland is a 50-year-old Pakistani man living in Warsaw's outskirts since 2017. He told us how he was selecting where to go, based on information obtained from his network:

Before, people are saying that time in 2017, '15, '16, '17 [in] Poland, immigration rule is very soft. And that's why I came here. [...] someone told me and, I told someone so many times, this is true. People are here and they are enjoying their life. [WP7_1]

Procedural issues were not the only reasons why he chose to settle in Poland. During the interview, the man described the social factors he took into account:

[...] when I got the Schengen visa, I [first] visited Sweden. Stockholm is [a] very, you know, European, rich country. I have experience. I lived there almost seven months. And honestly, I feel that they are people [who are] very reserved, very [strict]. But in Poland, people give you a smile, give you a response, give you a positive attention, positive response. I feel [the] people of Poland [are] better than other European countries like Sweden and Finland. I visit[ed] Finland, but I feel same situation [as in Sweden]. [WP7_1]

Among the group of people who declared much agency in movement and plan to settle in Poland, we identified several people who decided to leave their country due to security reasons. We spoke to three women from Ukraine who were beneficiaries of temporary protection obtained after the full-scale Russian invasion. They presented their migration to Poland as induced by the war but at the same time mentioned different reasons why they choose Poland as their destination country. One woman, currently over 50 years old, came to Warsaw in the first week after the invasion because her son was studying there. Another woman, 43, also migrated at the beginning of the invasion and spent four days traveling from eastern Ukraine to Poland. Due to a lack of tickets for direct connections, she had to change three times during her journey. She left her country for Slovakia but then decided to continue her travel to Poland. She explained:

Slovakia was transit-only. And due to the fact that before the war we visited and saw many countries, we had certain perceptions [...] And so we decided [to go to Poland]. [WP7_29]

The third female, almost 50, transited even more countries as she left Ukraine to Moldova, before entering the EU in Romania and then traveling via Hungary and Slovakia to Poland because she wanted to join her daughter who was studying there. She depicted her decision to leave Ukraine as well-thought through:

It so happened that I always knew that if there was a war, I would take the children out. This decision was made a very long time ago. I have a history education; I am a history teacher. And if you analyse it like this, almost all generations of us, well, among Ukrainians, we have always somehow, well, suffered from the fact that we are Russia's neighbours. [WP7_30]

These testimonies shed more light on the migration described in the literature as 'forced', which often minimises the scope of agency possessed by so-called 'forced migrants'. The women who left Ukraine demonstrated much agency in terms of making the decision to leave

(which often meant splitting up the family due to the obligation of men aged 18–60 to remain in the country) and where to leave, and then transiting through other countries to Poland.

A similar—or even more vivid—case was that regarding the people who travelled to Poland via Belarus from far-away countries located in the Middle East of Africa. We managed to interview several men who came to Poland irregularly via Belarus and applied for asylum. All of them depicted the journey through the forest as difficult and dangerous. As explained above, many migrants passing this route experience pushbacks by the Polish Border Guard. However, those who participated in our study and can be categorised as planning settlers managed to lodge an asylum application immediately after crossing the border.

The findings of our study confirm what was already established about the routes and difficulties during the journey, pointing out the agency of people who consciously decided to enter the EU via Belarus. An 18-year-old Sudanese man, awaiting a decision regarding international protection in Poland, presented his route by starting from the reasons to move and, then, briefly pointed out all countries passed:

That's where the war starts in Sudan. Everything is bad. They are killing everybody. They kill, and they burn our house and some things like that. Then I go to Ethiopia, then to Russia, then to Belarus, then to Poland. [WP7_18]

Our interviewees shared with us the stories of how they were preparing for such difficult travel. The first stage, impacting the decision to use this route, was collecting the necessary information. A 25-year-old man from Eritrea, also awaiting a decision on asylum in Poland, obtained information from the internet and friends. He described the organisational support he received prior to and during the journey, including the issuance of documents and one month of accommodation in a school in Belarus.

The migrants coming via this route had to navigate among the dangers or assistance at different parts while travelling. The Sudanese man quoted above depicted as support the actions of smugglers or Belarusian services with crossing the border, but the overall experience of the journey in the forest was described as very difficult and dangerous. At the same time, he declared the feeling that he would be able to endure such hardship. This is an important moment of agency that took the form of making a decision possibly bearing grave consequences. The man also mentioned the assistance from activists who helped him contact the Border Guard to apply for asylum (named ‘the police station’):

And you know, uh, it was dangerous and difficult, but I know I can do it. [...] And then we take a taxi from Minsk to the border. And I don't know how did they do that? But I think there's somebody who opened the border and let him open it and go, and we find it open. So, we jumped inside and then calling somebody who come to take us to this, to the police station. [...] It was difficult, everything. But I [knew I could] do it. If you believe in something, you can do it. Yes, I [knew] I will do it. It was very hard. It was very difficult. [...] some guy from Yemen [broke] his hand, but he's okay now. Everything is good. [WP7_18]

Another person who applied for asylum in Poland, a 24-year-old man from Sudan, told us that he had received a student visa to come to Russia and that a Belarusian soldier helped them to ‘open the wall’, which is how he entered the territory of Poland [WP7_20]. In turn, the Eritrean man mentioned above spent 10 or 12 days in the forest and described the behaviour of the Belarusian services in the following way:

It is very difficult. It is very problem[atic], like the army in Belarus. [It] is not good. Every time, if they get you, they hit you. They take your food. [WP7_19]

Therefore, although the travel was more or less meticulously planned in advance, it does not mean that it was realised according to these plans. As the collected testimonies show, the people experienced various difficulties while being on the move. However, the group quoted in this section managed to reach Poland and plan to settle there, as will be elaborated further in the next sections.

More in-depth knowledge about crossing the Polish-Belarusian border was obtained through the interview with an Afghani man who crossed the Polish-Belarusian border irregularly. He was initially considering staying in Russia but finally reached Germany. He decided to leave Russia because he received information that Russia had good relations with the Taliban. This resulted in a fear of deportation to Afghanistan. Next, after the experience of detention in Poland, he decided to migrate farther. As he said:

When the [Poland's] government doesn't want us, why do I have to stay here? So, I moved to Germany and I talked to my friends in Poland. All of them told me that, 'okay, go to Germany'. [WP7_14]

The decision to choose Germany over other European countries was made after collecting information about the legal and procedural reality in these countries, especially in terms of the waiting period for an asylum decision:

But now, Germany has better laws. You know, you have to wait just six months, and then you will receive the result [of the asylum procedure]. You know, they will help you or not. You will find it [out]. But in other countries like Switzerland or Netherlands or Sweden, you have to wait too long a time, and you have to move to a village out of the city, and you will become depressed. You cannot work. You know you will lose time. [WP7_14]

However, in Germany, he faced the possibility of the Dublin return to Poland, which he finally avoided thanks to the so-called 'church asylum'¹². Thus, the man manifested his agency in using all the possible options to realise his migration plan. He depicted this experience in the following way:

But this church that I was [at] there, you had to be Christian. You had to become a Christian. So I accepted, and I said, okay, no problem, I will be, uh, Christian if you help me, I will stay here. [WP7_14]

The story of this man is worth quoting in length to present how ambiguous the scope of agency possessed by people crossing the Polish-Belarusian border in an irregular way can be. In fact, they manifest much agency in planning and navigating between different actors, as it was presented in the section on spontaneous settlers. However, at the same time, they experience moments of extremely limited agency due to the border violence in both countries as well as dependency on smugglers. A moment of limited agency is detention, which becomes an experience for many migrants who manage to cross this border and apply for asylum in Poland, as was the case of this man:

¹² A scheme of assistance provided by a religious organisation to migrants facing a Dublin return recognised as members of vulnerable groups.

A TESTIMONY FROM THE POLISH-BELARUSIAN BORDER

by a 30-year-old Afghani man

I was an activist against the Taliban even until the last day when the Taliban came to Kabul; I was against them, you know, I was a really easy target. [...] I crossed the border from Belarus, and I was in the forest for eight days. After eight days, you know, activists in Poland came to me. And they help us when they ... when we move to camp close to Wędrzyn. [...] We arrived to Poland, but two times security guards send us back to Belarus in the forest. And it was the worst experience I had because we didn't have food, water, or anything. [...] a lawyer came to us in Poland, in the forest in Poland, and called the other media to come there. And because of the media, the police couldn't send us back to Belarus. And they helped us. [...] Yeah, we were the first group that arrived there after this problem, and then we paid for that. But this person [a smuggler] was, you know, lying. He didn't have any information because he didn't cross the border before. Yeah, just he said, go to this location and then cross this border. And then there is a taxi. They will help you. But no, when I ... when we arrived to the border, we crossed the border, and we saw that all thousands of these soldiers are there, and we were between them. Belarusian soldiers told us that you have to go to Poland. You cannot come back. We said that we have visa. We have passports and everything. Because with a Russian visa, you can go to Belarus. But they didn't accept because their plan was to force [us] to the Polish border. And the Polish border said that 'Oh, you are illegal. We cannot help you. You have to [go] back to Belarus. Uh, like a football, you know [...] Belarusian soldiers with dog, they [tore] some [of my belongings], for example, my coats and my pants. So in the forest in this weather, I was, like, naked, you know, without clothes, and it was hard. So, I tried to cover my food and this part of my jacket with tape, you know, tape. [...] they [Belarusian soldiers] forced the dog to [attack] us. You know, my friend in the face, me in the hand. All of us, you know, they beat us and with electric shocker. [...] they put something [a cover] on our head and move us nowhere. I don't know where, [...] 'Okay. It is your last time. If you don't cross the border to Poland, we will kill you here'. [WP7_14]

Integration

There is no one pattern of integration among the migrants who planned their travel to Poland and declare that they would like to settle here. However, the common element is using different networks to receive the assistance necessary for realising the planned steps of the movement. These networks mostly consisted of family and friends. The man from Pakistan, already staying in Poland for seven years, was able to organise his life in a new country thanks to the assistance he received from his brother. As he said:

When I came here before, I didn't have any job in Poland. So that time, my brother sent me money. [...] He is living in Sweden so that ... almost one year here he is helping me. After one year, I [can stand on my own two feet]. And I am working normally and living on my own. [WP7_1]

Regarding relations with the host society, the man explained that he is very busy with his job and this makes it difficult to maintain intensive social relations. He declared having some

friends in Poland, mostly also with a migrant background, and meeting them two or three times a month.

The people who crossed the border with Belarus and applied for international protection were staying in open reception centres. They declared maintaining ties with other asylum applicants from their countries of origin staying in the same place. The remote location of the centre made it difficult to develop relations with the host society, so as the uncertain and temporary status while awaiting the decision regarding asylum. Despite that fact, the men interviewed by us declared the will to learn Polish and continue their education here.

It was different in the case of Ukrainian women who were beneficiaries of temporary protection. Despite the general high level of employment among this group¹³, the women interviewed by us had not found employment. However, this does not necessarily have to be an indicator of a low level of integration. In the cases of our interviewees, they had sufficiently strong support from their social network that allowed them to attend Polish language classes in order to improve their language skills up to the point that made it possible to find a job suitable to their qualifications. This is an important finding that contributes to the knowledge about the possible wasting of social capital regarding employment of highly qualified Ukrainian beneficiaries of temporary protection in jobs that do not require such education or professional experience. These people also have high potential for integration. One woman, almost 50 years old, graduated in economics and pedagogy, presented her relations with the hosting society in the following way:

Oh great! I'm probably lucky. I only met here, well, very, let's say, loyal Poles towards Ukrainians. I study a lot here. I've met a lot of teachers and people here who, well, are quite educated, they understand what's happening, they understand this whole terrible situation. [WP7_30]

Not all experiences were so positive, but other examples confirm that the social network, especially in terms of relations with Polish citizens, contributes to more possibilities. One woman, 43, who was a dentist in Ukraine, told us that the landlady of the flat where she lives declared that she has no problem with letting the flat as long as the Polish partner of the interviewed woman lives there, but if they broke up, she would not continue the contract with the Ukrainian woman. The interviewee concluded this story with the words:

There is a bit of an attitude that is not trusting; it seems to me that they [Poles] don't really want us as Ukrainians. But in principle, the situation is normal. There are normal Poles, and there are not so good ones, depends on who you meet. [WP7_29]

According to our findings, the language—despite some significant similarities between Polish and Ukrainian—was a serious obstacle, both in the practical and formal aspects. The woman who struggles to work again as a dentist described in detail the process of striving to obtain documents allowing her to practice in Poland. Another woman, already over 50, explained that her involvement in assistance for other Ukrainians made it difficult to improve her Polish language skills:

The younger son integrated faster because he went straight away to the Polish high school, to the first class of the high school for that moment and he learned the language faster. And I was working in a humanitarian organisation and there I was working all

¹³ Up to 65% (PIE 2024).

the time with our refugees and I'm still taking courses and studying Polish, but unfortunately, I have no practice. So still, language for me is a problem. [WP7_28]

The agency of these women was also manifested by the fact that they—recognizing the need to improve their language skills—were participating in Polish classes accessible through one NGO.

Possible return or further mobility

As the name of this category suggests, the planning settlers declared openly their desire to stay in Poland for a longer time. This was mainly due to security reasons based on which the migrants excluded the possibility of return to their country. Mostly they were referring to the ongoing war and repeating stories linked to the reasons for leaving their countries. For instance, a 25-year-old man from Eritrea who applied for asylum in Poland answered very briefly the question about possible return: ‘it is dangerous, so I cannot go’ [WP7_19]. The 18-year-old Sundanese man in the same legal situation explained that the return would be:

Too dangerous. I think I cannot go back again. I will never because they kill everybody. Even your baby, even woman, man. Everything is bad. They kill anybody. So, I can't go back. If you go ... If I go back, they will kill me. [WP7_18]

The men interviewed by us excluded also moving to another country. It should be mentioned that this is difficult to assess these statements because according to the Dublin regulations, people in asylum procedures should stay in the country where they applied for protection. Therefore, statements about plans to stay in Poland could be made due to the feeling that this is the ‘proper’ answer. The Afghani man staying currently in Germany offered the same response. He told us, recalling also difficulties endured during the journey and an effort to integrate:

Currently, I have a chance to go to the USA because I was working for them. [...] But I have to wait. And I don't want to move, you know, because I tried my [hardest]. I tried hard to learn language and find friends and find a way to make money, you know, to stay here. Yeah, I don't want to move to any other country. I want to stay here, and I don't want to go back to Afghanistan. [WP7_14]

The women who left Ukraine after the full-scale invasion and were currently beneficiaries of temporary protection—in principle—did not plan to go back to Ukraine. However, their statements were not as firm as in the case of people who crossed the Polish-Belarusian border. The female interviewee who was a dentist in Ukraine explained that she invested in integrating so she does not want to leave Poland or move to another country. She said, referring to her struggles about the right to practice dentistry again:

No, here you go through such a difficult path to get legalised as a specialist and [start over] again. Well, I don't have 20 years, you know? [WP7_29]

At the same time, the only concern for her was the situation of her parents staying in Ukraine. Currently, her sisters are taking care of their parents, but, as she said:

I don't know what will happen if ... If everyone [all the sisters] left. If they are forced to leave, I don't know how the parents will be. This is the only thing that cannot be forced or convinced. [WP7_29]

In some cases, however, the decision changed over time—also was not unequivocally presented during the interview. The woman over 50 who came to Poland with her younger son to join the older one explained her family situation and feelings about return with no full certainty about her plans:

When we came to Poland, we thought [we would return] soon. Well, our government told us that it would be soon, we were going home and so on. Well, now personally, I don't see the end of this war yet. That's the first thing. Dangerous there. The front is not far from my city. [...] The elder son graduated from university here. I won't come back home. Younger [son]... well, now he has started college, so he has to finish his studies first. He will then decide for himself. But I don't think he'll go home anymore, because he's already used to having friends and colleagues here. He found it, I think my younger son won't go home either. Well, as for me, I don't know, we'll see. [WP7_28]

Another female, being almost 50, explained that she wants to settle in Poland but she is very concerned about her future. Due to her health situation, she cannot work, so returning to Ukraine would entail difficulties with continuing treatment to a satisfactory standard. In case the temporary protection is not prolonged, she would be forced to legalise her stay either on labour grounds or apply for asylum which is also not a certain path.

Health issues were also an important reason to settle in Poland for the 50-year-old Pakistani man. He told us about his heart problems and explained that Pakistani medical care does not guarantee proper treatment for him. He said:

I'm sure if I got two heart attack in my country, I never would never get this second life. [...] First thing is my health, my medical situation. If I go back, I don't have a money to continue my treatment. [WP7_1]

Thus, in the case of settlement plans, the agency of this category of migrants was seriously hampered by the conditions in their countries of origin. However, they still had the possibility to move to another country within the Schengen zone (although facing Dublin returns in case of asylum applicants).

'Spontaneous settlers'

Migrants included in the category of spontaneous settlers were not planning precisely their travel to Poland. As the presented example shows, coming here was a result of a coincidence of forces perceived by them as external (e.g., migration regimes). After such an experience of mobility, these migrants express the will to stay in Poland for a longer time.

Agency in movement

Spontaneity in the case of mobility means that migrants did not present their travel to Poland as their decision. They left their countries for different reasons, but what was common among them was the feeling that they were not in control of the migration process. One example is the situation of a 31-year-old Chechen man, a father of five children, who told us that after his Dublin return to Poland, he decided not to move anywhere else:

I happened to stay here, one might say, during the course of my trip. It turned out that other countries did not accept me, I was returned back to this country. But after

returning, I no longer went to other places, I just wanted to stabilise [my situation] because I was on the road for a long time. [WP7_7]

Thus, as he explained, staying in Poland for a longer time was not his initial plan. However, he was in a way forced to do so by the external factor of the Dublin regulation. It can be argued that his situation was similar to the man quoted in the previous section who crossed the Polish-Belarusian border. Both of them declared that their migration experience so far was—at least regarding the route—following their plan to travel via Belarus to the first safe country in the EU. This is why their narratives manifest the feeling of possessing control over the migration process, however, in fact it was to some extent shaped by the Belarusian services and smugglers. In the case of the Chechen man quoted above, the Dublin regulation impacted and changed his trajectory contrary to his will.

A 38-year-old Tajik woman said that she came to Poland in 2020 because it was the only option for her to receive the medical treatment she needed. Currently, she is awaiting a decision regarding international protection. She recalls the process of deciding to leave her country in the following way:

I was disabled as a child and I had surgery here as a child. And for this reason, I had ... to have another operation. As for my referral, all the medical documents were in this country, and therefore for this reason, I came here. [WP7_15]

Her words expressed a lack of agency, rather a feeling of being unable to make her decision freely. The woman also added that she made her decision together with her husband and, after receiving treatment, they decided more or less freely to stay in Poland for a longer time:

I usually consult with my husband [...] and resolve all our difficult situations. [...] We decided to move here to have surgery, continue to study, get a job, adapt here, and stay. Naturally. [WP7_15]

In another example, a Ukrainian woman over 60 who came to Poland in 2010 includes an incident of deception by a company in Poland that resulted in the loss of her legal status. She said that she came to Poland ‘just by accident’ to take care of an elderly lady and depicted her mobility as ‘fate’. [WP7_10]. Later on, she explained how she was deceived by the company:

They took money, bribes from me, but they did not explain to me that they only made me a stay permit for 100 days, 3 months. And our agreement was that I would stay there for six months. Also, when I was here, when I explained it to myself and, how can I say, I checked the documents and I saw that it wasn't like that. It was either I had to leave and do it again and again for a bribe, or I had to stay. Yes? Well, that's it. These people asked me to stay. And I stayed. [WP7_10]

Therefore, migrants' agency is limited not only by state policies but also by the deception of private companies that take advantage of people's lack of knowledge or difficult situations. This interviewee explained that she could not take advantage of the amnesty in 2012 due to too short of a stay in Poland but she decided to stay irregularly hoping for the next amnesty, which did not occur. Then, she found herself in a precarious situation. She recalled the period without documentation:

I was too afraid. I couldn't buy a [e.g., monthly] bus ticket. I had to shop every day. It was very difficult. I couldn't get to the [public] doctors. I had to do it [medical care] all in private. I was afraid of everyone... [WP7_10]

Her second key decision was when her daughter joined her and needed support paying university fees. The woman told us:

[My] daughter came to study. She got into the University of Warsaw. And I had to stay here to work and pay for my child's university. There was no choice. [WP7_10]

Therefore, she decided to prolong her irregular stay because her daughter had joined her and she needed money for university fees. The woman used the words 'there was no choice' [pl. 'nie było wyjścia'] to describe her feeling of a lack of agency over this decision.

Although for many people it could be perceived as a deliberate choice, our interviewee depicted it as an obvious decision based on her family obligations by using a very strong description of the compulsory nature of the decisions she had made. Her feelings of helplessness are reflected in the following words:

I decided for myself. I was afraid to ask someone here. I was afraid of my shadow then. Because if I left, the child won't [be able to] pay for the university. [WP7_10]

The feeling of having to make the decision regarding mobility because of children was also expressed by a 42-year-old Chechen man from Grozny who applied for asylum in Poland in 2022. He recalls his migration experience in the following way:

[B]ecause I expressed my opinion, persecution began against me, cases began to be filed, and I had to drop everything and leave there [...] If this concerned only me and the issue would have been closed, then I probably would not have left. [...] But when the psyche of children breaks down... [WP7_6].

It has to be emphasised that in the case of Chechens, the route via Belarus is the most common path to claim asylum; however, this is not the same route used as in the case of the people whose testimonies were presented in the previous section. Chechens, as Russian citizens, can enter Belarus by official means of transport, such as a train, which is the most popular way to get to the EU border in Terespol. This is where usually Russian citizens of North Caucasus origin apply for asylum in Poland. This is why travelling to Poland was not the same endeavour as in the case of the quoted people from Eritrea or Sudan. However, it also has to be noted that in the case of asylum-seekers, it could be sometimes problematic to leave the territory of the Chechen Republic. Also, since 2016 there are reported cases of the Polish Border Guard in Terespol refusing to accept to lodge an asylum application (Szczepanik 2018). The man quoted above said that prior to coming to Poland, he consulted his case with a lawyer from a Polish NGO. The final decision to come was a result of this consultation:

But I decided that I might take a chance. And I came. He [the lawyer] prepared all the documents. I don't know if it was an appeal to the commandant or whatever it was. I came to the border, and with [a bit of] grief they let me through. [WP7_6]

In this case, the decision was rather about coming to Poland or staying in Chechnya due to the lack of other possible choices (after the Russian full-scale invasion of Ukraine there are fewer routes from Russia to the EU). This is different from the situation of people from countries like Sudan or Eritrea for whom Poland is not the most obvious destination.

Some migrants included in the category of spontaneous settlers described their migration to Poland as happening for reasons other than concerns about security in their previous places of stay. This was the case of a 26-year-old Palestinian man from Lebanon who was studying in Turkey before coming to Poland. He said:

I came here for Erasmus. It wasn't planned. It was, uh, just something that happened. I saw the city. I made a lot of good friends. I eventually met my girlfriend. [WP7_5]

Therefore, migration to Poland in this case was not a plan but rather something 'that happened' because the Erasmus programme is assumed to be a short-term stay. Moreover, the narrative of this man is not centred on the decision-making process to come to Poland but rather on factors that shaped his mobility plans as developing various kinds of social bounds.

A similar story was shared by a 21-year-old trans-man from Uzbekistan whose decision to come to Poland resulted from a hint by a friend of his to look at some information found on social media. He said he left his country because of a lack of acceptance of his sexual identity and difficulty to realise his dreams to become a singer and an actor. He described the decision-making process in the following way:

I was sitting at home [...] And suddenly, my friend told me that he found from Instagram some website to apply for universities and [from] abroad, Europe[an] countries. And I chose suddenly Poland because, like, I just thought it's, like, easier to go to Poland for studying, for living, and, like, it's, like, [Slavic] language, you know, like, I'm, I'm good at because I have ... I used to study the Russian language [in] Russian school. So, it was, it's so good for me. I just [write to] Poland for [a new] beginning [in] your country and I just applied for university and like three months I got the visa. [WP7_27]

In his case, the man's spontaneous decision resulted in surprise amongst his friends but also in fear when the time came to enact his plan. He recalled:

It was so, like, my friends told me, 'oh my God, you took off so fast'. And I said, 'because I, like, I have decided for this and I have tried my best and three months visa' and I came here and, like, I was so happy that I was, like, coming here. But when I took a ticket for ... like for plane. So, I just went there. [I thought], 'Oh my God, what I'm doing. I don't know anything about there. And [why] I'm going there. I will try my best.' And I came here, like, 'yes, it was like on Instagram'. So, nice story. [WP7_27]

Some of our interviewees made the decision about their mobility by drawing on unclear information about their destinations. This was the case of a 25-year-old Iraqi man who reached Poland in 2021 irregularly via Belarus and, after lodging an asylum application, was placed in a detention centre. This part of his story is similar to those depicted in the previous section. However, after receiving a negative decision, he moved to Germany, where he applied for asylum anew. According to the interview, it was not his initial plan to reach Germany but rather a result of the outcome of the asylum procedure in Poland. He explained why he chose to reach Germany, mentioning vaguely his not fully verified (as he repeated twice the phrase 'I heard') information about accessible assistance:

I think Germany is the best because now I have only information about Germany. [...] in Germany I have this organisation when some people, I heard, [...] some family or some single person they want to deport [...] and this organisation, they help him and give him some money to find work. [WP7_9]

Similarly, a woman from the Russian North Caucasus talked vaguely about the uneasy fear of meeting people who might persecute them. As we will present in further sections, the fear of diaspora members was sometimes recalled by interviewees as a factor in their mobility within the EU. The woman, who received asylum and lives in eastern Poland, told us:

I don't know why, but there was a feeling that it was safer here, like in some countries, I won't name them. Probably everyone ... Everyone has friends and relatives here. But where we are now is more reliable, there are no people to be afraid of or worry about. [WP7_25]

In sum, the migrants included in the category of spontaneous settlers perceive their mobility as not fully resulting from their agency and meticulous planning. Instead, they depicted different external factors, varying from necessity to coincidence.

Integration

Spontaneous settlers developed relatively strong ties with the host society, which strengthened their plans to settle in the place where they are living. Interestingly, the integration process was often driven by the spontaneity of their mobility, which resulted in weak links to the communities from their countries of origin. Most of our interviewees said that they receive support from friends in the place where they live. The Palestinian man from Lebanon quoted earlier said that most of his friends, or even all, are Polish. The 42-year-old Chechen man told us, recalling also the lawyer from the NGO who helped him with lodging the asylum application, that:

There are people who help me, they helped me a lot when I crossed the border. [...] The person helped me a lot and still helps me with advice, [action], and support. [WP7_6]

Also, the Iraqi man who moved to Germany after being refused asylum in Poland pointed out the NGO, in his case Caritas (the charitable organisation of the Catholic Church), as a crucial source of support in his destination country. He explained that the assistance is necessary because he does not speak German, and without the interpretation support, he would not be able to cope with the asylum procedures.

Similarly, the Tajik woman awaiting examination of her asylum application in Poland expressed how difficult it is to integrate in terms of the language barrier. She also mentioned other logistical and organisational issues like enrolling children to the schooling system, however, she was also firm about her intent to endure all the hardship she experienced:

Here it is sometimes difficult to integrate and learn the language. But if the family also encounters hard problems with the children, well, it will be quite difficult here. This is not inevitable and you can face it everywhere, because our language is different, we do not speak a foreign language so well, and here we will face it. The problem is first with the language, then adapting, getting the children into school, kindergarten, and getting a job. This is very problematic. We have to get through it all, it's difficult. [WP7_15]

Integration was easier in the case of labour or educational migration as it was based on more interaction with Polish society than awaiting a decision regarding international protection. The trans-man from Uzbekistan describes integration as familiarising, or 'getting used to' living in a given place due to daily activities:

I'm working and studying here, so I know a lot of things in Poland, like the places, the people. So I'm, like, getting used to [it]. [WP7_27]

In his case, integration resulted in support received from friends, which was crucial to enduring emotional hardship. He shared with us his personal story of ending a relationship with his boyfriend:

I broke up with my boyfriend like three weeks ago, and I was crying. I was so bad, feeling like, oh, I just need to leave. I can't live here. [...] you know, memory is like playing with me in my mind. So, it was so bad. Not ... I can't sleep, I couldn't eat something or some, uh, going to work now. And my friends came to me. They helped me 24/7. [WP7_27]

In some cases, the migrants were not only receiving support in the destination country but also were themselves the source of support for their families back home. The woman from Ukraine staying in Poland since 2010 told us that her integration process has been marked by helping her mother in Ukraine:

I'm sending money, I'm sending a bag [of goods], I'm sending more money so that my aunt can take care of her sister. Now, the neighbours still deal with it. For now, yes. [Wp7_10]

This means that she has to allocate some resources earned in Poland to materially support her family in Ukraine.

Integration can be distorted by the fear of deportation. The 43-year-old woman from the Russian North Caucasus presented situations she lived through and her feelings afterwards:

I was very afraid of deportation when we had no status. Of course, it was very scary because we had one case when they wanted to deport us. I was just lucky that one of my daughters was not at home that day. She was with a friend. But it was a very scary picture when they broke into our room at 03:00, when we were sleeping, they opened the door themselves and turned on the light. And so it was a shock. Certainly. 'Get up, get dressed quickly!' They could at least come back [later], so I [could] get dressed ... They were all men, yes, but there were two women. When I said, 'come back, I would at least [be] dressed then', the men turned away, but two women came in and ... looked at me. [WP7_25]

The fear of deportation was also visible in the narrative of the 42-year-old Chechen who applied for asylum in Poland thanks to the assistance of an NGO:

And ... at the moment, there is anxiety, worry, anticipation. [...] I feel protected and safe. But the problem is that all this could end tomorrow morning. Tomorrow morning you receive a refusal and they can simply come in the morning, take you, put you on a plane and send you home. [WP7_6]

Possible return or further mobility

The category of migrants described in this section expressed their will to stay in the place where they currently live. However, some of our interviewees expressed nostalgia, even if they had bad memories from their home country. The trans-man from Uzbekistan told us:

But, you know, like, it's my, like, my country, my home country. Like, no matter what, no matter what bad, no matter what something, I will just miss [it]. [WP7_27]

A similar feeling of missing one's country of origin was manifested in the narrative of the 25-year-old Iraqi man who entered Poland in 2021 irregularly via Belarus and, after being in a detention camp, moved to Germany where he is awaiting an asylum decision:

I had [many] friends in my country and I had [...] other family like uncle, cousin, was like this, you know, in Middle East, people have [much] contact with family, like son of cousin, son of uncle [...] And of course, I miss him. Uh, and also, I miss my country. I miss my culture. Yes. Because of that, I want to go back, but not [forever]. Like only tourists, for 2 or 3 weeks for meeting [people]. [WP7_9]

The will to settle in Poland was presented as a result of a mix of integration efforts and dangerous situations in the country of origin. The Palestinian man told us about his possible return to Palestine or other Arab countries where he previously resided:

We were not sure yet, but for now, Poland is a perfect choice for us. I'm learning the language and I got used to the country already. [...] you have freedom of speech. You can, like, say stuff that you wouldn't be able to say in, you know, Lebanon or the Emirates. I feel more, like, you know, more like myself, more like a human being here [WP7_5]

He added that he could consider returning only when the situation in Palestine was stable and the threats to a dignified life disappeared:

Just a condition of peace. No war, safety, and no racism, no segregation, no apartheid. No genocide. Like what's happening right now in Gaza and Palestine. So, these are my conditions that I would come back to my country. [WP7_5]

The will to stay in Poland resulting from the fear of returning to the country of origin was also visible in the narrative of the Tajik woman awaiting a decision regarding asylum. Interestingly, when speaking about the reasons for leaving Tajikistan, she described her health situation. However, when asked about the potential return, the woman recalled security concerns in her country of origin:

We had a situation where people returning home disappeared from the airport. Yes. And no one knows where they are, what happened to them, no one knows about it. [WP7_15]

A similar story was told by the woman from the Russian North Caucasus when she was asked about the situation of returnees in her region of origin:

Naturally, nothing good happens to them. Or they disappear, or something else. [WP7_25]

The woman also mentioned the fear of letting her children go to live with their father, from whom they escaped:

I worry about the children who are at risk, if they are at risk of being separated from me. This is first of all. Secondly, they will return to their father, and there, the hellish life they had will begin [again, from] which I brought them. And it was very difficult for me to bring them. It's not easy. In any case, they still have consequences. [...] we don't want to go anywhere because [...] for] children, stress comes with moving, with new neighbours, with a new school. [WP7_25]

Noteworthy, several people declared that they had already changed the country in which they reside or would consider such a change if facing deportation to their country of origin. The 42-year-old Chechen man awaiting his asylum decision in one of the cities in eastern Poland told us:

I believe that the country in which I am now is optimal for me and for my family in terms of raising children, work, adaptation, and everything else. [... As for the] threat of deportation to my homeland. This is the only thing that could do this [force him to migrate further] [...] Because in addition to what happened and the fact that I left, this will be a one-way ticket for me. [WP7_6]

He even emphasised this opinion with the words:

It's better to die here than to go home. For what? Why subject yourself to torture and humiliation when you will die in the end anyway? [WP7_6]

Some people were taking into consideration the integration of their children, already occurring in Poland. The 38-year-old Tajik woman explained:

No, I want to stay here for now. Here, I have small children, they went to school, in kindergartens and learned a little of the language. That's why I don't want to. I want to stay so that my children learn the language properly and don't miss school. [WP7_15]

The woman from Ukraine [WP_10] who was deceived by her employer, when asked about the possibility of either returning or migrating elsewhere, pointed out the dangers of the war and the need to improve her English skills as constraints that hamper potential moves.

‘Planning nomads’

Some people expressed a high level of agency in planning their travel; however, they have not yet decided about their future, including a potential return. In the case of some people, their further mobility was imposed on them by the migration system, and they feel being in a nomadic situation with the will to further migrate elsewhere. This is the smallest category in our sample, as among our interviewees, a plan to reach a concrete destination was seldom linked to a lack of a plan to settle there.

Agency in movement

For the 27-year-old man from Morocco, who had already been deported from Poland after staying there two years, leaving his country was a planned effort that faced attempts by his family to stop it. His mother even offered him money if he did not emigrate, but he refused because of his need for independence:

I always wanted to leave, to be independent from my parents. [...] my mother at the beginning, when I was going to Poland, she didn't accept the idea. She even offered me money to study in my country. But I told her 'no, I want to do everything by myself. I want to apply by myself, pay everything by myself'. [WP7_2]

The man recalled that his friend was sharing with him his own migration experience, which became the basis for his decision to choose Poland as the destination country, mainly due to the costs of studying at a university:

[H]e applied to Poland and he went to Poland, to Opole. So, we were in contact and he told me, here is good. Studies are cheaper compar[ed] with other countries. [WP7_2]

In the narrative of this man, return was a difficult experience resulting in problems with adaptation. He declared that there was no security concern in his case but that returning and possibly remaining in Morocco would be disappointing for his family, which expected him to be a success through emigration, even though they were against it in the beginning:

There was no risk. Nothing. But ... But there was big disappointment. It was a very disappointing situation because I'm the eldest son. I have three young siblings, and I'm like an example for them. And it was [that] they were even in shock as well when I came back like ... Without [anything]. I was working, I was studying, and then I came back not doing anything. Unemployed. Uh, not doing anything. So, there was a shock at the beginning. [WP7_2]

After his forced return he migrated to Turkey, and he depicted his life there as a temporary stage in his life. He expressed the will to migrate again to Poland for educational reasons, but overall, he expressed his readiness for remaining mobile and experiencing a cosmopolitan lifestyle:

Turkey for me now is just an experience, like a passing experience in my life. I would like to pass time here, get more experience from here, learn their languages. If it's possible, of course. I started learning a little bit, and, yeah, it will be a good experience for me because I'm social. I like to meet new people, learn about other cultures, learn other languages. I'm speaking, by the way, many languages. So, that's my hobby. So, I like meeting new people and discovering new cultures. [WP7_2]

A similar pattern was observed in the case of a 24-year-old man from Sri Lanka without documentation who decided to come to Poland, drawing on information from both his friend's experience and the internet:

It was actually I chose it because of my friend who came one year ago to Poland. So, he helped me really to come to Poland. Okay. So, that's how I started my life in Poland. [...] Before I checked everything and the weather. Actually, that's what I like, the winter. [WP7_26]

Integration

Our interviewees categorised as planning nomads had not any common experience with integration in Poland as their situation varied considerably from case to case. The Sri Lankan man, who currently does not have documentation to stay, described the strong ties he developed with Polish society, which resulted in, in his opinion, a good amount of knowledge about Poland:

I usually take information about Poland and everything from my Polish friends. I have a lot of Polish friends here. So, like I have a good connection with them. So, I talk to them every time. That's how I get information about Poland. [WP7_26]

In the case of the Moroccan man who had to go back to his country, he described the story of losing his legal stay, which happened due to a misunderstanding with his employer. It resulted in his decision to leave Poland before the return would be enforced:

[W]hen I got the information that I should [return] to my country because I'm illegal and this might create some problems for me, I just booked the flight and I took my luggage and I just left because [...] I don't want problems. [...] I didn't choose what happened to me. It was a misunderstanding between me and between the company where I was [working]. They didn't take care of the demand, my demand, my request to apply for the TRC [permit of stay] ... which was their mistake. They didn't do anything. [WP7_2]

Possible return or further mobility

The planning nomads were taking into consideration further mobility for various reasons. What is important is the planned character of their future mobility, as our interviewees presented various factors influencing further movement. The 27-year-old man from Morocco who was deported from Poland after staying there two years and is currently living in Turkey, described his plans for the future as including a potential return to Morocco, but different from the first time. As he presented it, he experienced negative attitudes from his family after he was required to return (precisely, he returned on his own before the decision was enforced). In the future, he considers returning possible if it is a success story:

I have this idea in my mind, but I'm not thinking about this soon. I would like to get more experience, develop myself, learn more languages, and speak fluently. All of them. And, well, if I want to come back to my country, I will come back with a big plus. And I would like to change something in my country that I learned from other countries. [WP7_2]

Sometimes, return is constrained by the lack of legal status, which hampers mobility across national and Schengen borders. For instance, the 24-year-old man from Sri Lanka without documentation to stay would consider returning. Still, for now, he is constrained by his lack of legal status in Poland, possibly by the fear of an entry ban to the Schengen Zone issued with an order to leave:

As soon as I'm legal here, I will go back to my country. [...] In Sri Lanka actually I will feel nothing to worry about. I will feel safe. [WP7_26]

While returning was not an option for most of our interviewees, many were considering moving to another country. As with returns, sometimes people were looking for the best option for their life, like the Sri Lankan man quoted above who talked about the potential for migration from Poland to other European countries, Scandinavian ones in particular:

I feel like maybe I can find another good position in my job in these countries. [WP7_26]

Thus, the nomadic experience is linked to looking for better possibilities on the labour market.

‘Spontaneous nomads’

This profile includes a relatively large number of people who perceive themselves as not fully controlling their past and future mobility process, or—concerning the future—at least they do not plan to settle in the place where they currently live.

Agency in movement

Similar to spontaneous settlers, the migrants described in this section often presented their migration to Poland as not being part of a well-thought-through process. A 28-year-old man from Turkey, waiting for renewal of his temporary stay permit, described how his migration to Poland was a result of coincidence:

It was quite funny story. [...] I needed to say some excuse to my family to go to Istanbul, you know, because I was always going and they are saying, okay, enough and I saw one exhibition ... for university in foreign countries. [...] And I went to Istanbul. Of course, I went to party. And, you know, it was just an excuse, [the] exhibition. But after that party, I [told myself I need to respect] my family, so, it's better to go to this exhibition at least. [...] there was one stand, he told me: 'okay, take your luggage. I will take you to Poland in two months. He said he was saying like 100%. [...] It was my plan to come to Europe to grow a business. It happened like that. [...] If he would say, take your luggage, I will take you to, for example, Italy or another country. I would go there. [...] He was [going to] Poland. [WP7_4]

In another case, a 38-year-old man from Bangladesh, who came to Poland in 2020 to study, explained:

I was applying to a few different countries as well. I was applying to the University of Prague, Charles [University] in Prague, also in Germany, Finland, etc., but this university [in Lublin] went super-fast, which was the only reason I came here. [WP7_13]

A considerable number of the narratives about the reasons for movement presented by the interviewees was built on security issues. Our interviewees indicated various threats to themselves or their families stemming from human-rights violations, political instability, or conservative family customs in the country of origin. Importantly, migrants depict their scope of agency differently, pointing out either that decisions were imposed on them by the situation or that they deliberately weighed various factors, often in one statement.

A 42-year-old woman from Dagestan, who, after applying for asylum in Poland, moved to Germany and finally avoided a Dublin return from there thanks to the so-called ‘church asylum’, underlined that she did not leave her place of origin due to economic reasons but only because of security problems:

You know, I didn't leave because I felt bad there. I felt very good there because we had our own business, we had everything. [WP7_17]

In this case, mobility resulted in splitting up a family, a situation imposed by the migration system. As mentioned, the woman benefited from ‘church asylum’, but it was not possible in the case of her sons:

And the church asylum helped us to avoid Dublin [return]. They helped a lot, but they could not help their sons. They said that since they are healthy guys, they do not have a disease, and we cannot. [WP7_17]

In turn, a Kurdish woman from Turkey, who crossed the Polish-Belarusian border and later was returned to Turkey, explained how entangled the reasons why she fled her country were, including domestic violence and ethnic discrimination:

I was abused by my own father when I was very young, then I was ostracised by the family, and all kinds of things happened to me, then my family came after me, and I had no choice but to run away. [...] When Batman or any other province in the Southeast [of Turkey] is written on our identity cards, this causes us problems in many areas in the West, such as renting a house or getting a job. [WP7_23]

An important finding in our study on this matter is the fact that some of the participants have already experienced migration between several countries (sometimes including return to the country of origin). The 30-year-old Tajik man, who, after staying in Poland as an asylum-seeker, moved to Italy and received protection there, recalled how migration from Poland to Estonia resulted in forced return to Tajikistan, which, in turn, led to problems with the security services of his country:

I came with a visa for the first time in 2021. I was fine. We lived in Poland, went to Estonia and were deported to our homeland. After that, there was a problem when we were taken away. I didn't have any problems with the KGB of Tajikistan at all. That's when they took us away; they handed us over to them. It started from that moment. [WP7_16]

The woman from Dagestan openly told us that she regrets migrating from Poland to Italy because of her fear that the diaspora in Poland will denounce her. When asked what she would change in her previous experiences and choices, she answered:

The only thing is, I would not leave Poland. My big mistake. And it was [I] who initiated this. Because I was afraid that Poland was closer to Russia. And I thought if I went, the farther from Russia, the better it would be. This is my big mistake, which I regret. [WP7_17]

Integration

Integration includes re-integration in the country of origin (or any other place of return) after being returned. Our findings show that the process of adaptation of returnees can be seriously hampered by the forced character of the return, which can result in trauma. For the Kurdish woman from Turkey, who crossed the Polish-Belarusian border and later was deported to Turkey, the return was a traumatising experience:

Deportation, it was devastation for me to return to Turkey after being detained for a year in a closed camp. I can't [re-]integrate. Nothing is the same as before. I have lost my work environment; I have lost my ground. [...] after I came back, I started having psychological problems. A constant state of stress like anxiety. Yes, like panic attacks. This happened after my return. [...] When I was in Europe, I was thinking that OK, I am saved, this place is a salvation for me, I will start a new life. Now that I am back again, I don't feel that I belong here. I never have. [WP7_23]

The woman commented on the attitude of Kurdish society towards returnees, which she contests:

They laugh at the returnees. They mock them, frankly. Here, you couldn't do it, you failed [...] I think they would be ashamed to call me a failure. Because it is a very difficult route. [WP7_23]

Return was a difficult experience hampering reintegration also for a 26-old-Chechen woman who was attempting to enter Poland via the Terespol-Brest border crossing. After several unsuccessful attempts, she decided to return to Chechnya. As she recalls:

I returned here [to Chechnya] about two weeks ago. And so, I was in Brest for two and half, about three months. I couldn't live there anymore. There was no longer any possibility further. Now I am in Chechnya and I remain in a very difficult situation. My gas, electricity, and water were turned off. [WP7_22]

The woman pointed out that she does not feel comfortable after the return, and if it was possible, she would surely decide to re-emigrate to Poland.

A very important finding is in regards to relations with the diaspora, as some interviewees expressed their fear of compatriots. In some cases, it led to further migration from Poland. The 30-year-old man from Tajikistan told us about his reasons for moving from Poland to Italy:

I felt comfortable in Poland. After they threatened me, they called from Tajikistan, from the Organised Crime Control Department, they called me and called me, they even said the addresses where I lived. 'We'll get you back anyway.' And [because of] this I had to leave Poland. It became uncomfortable there. Because there really are a lot of our people there. I thought, where ours are not, I should go there. [WP7_16]

The woman from Dagestan, who, after applying for asylum in Poland, moved to Germany and finally avoided a Dublin return from there, told a similar story:

Those who lived there began to tell us that there were our people there who could knock and tell where my sons were. That's the fear of it. [WP7_17]

A very detailed story about the relations with diaspora was shared with us by the Bangladeshi man:

A lot of Bangladeshis who are living here, they would know me, but I don't know many of them. I only know 2 or 3 people. And also, there is a reason why I stay away from them, or why I keep myself away from them because, let's say in Warsaw, yeah, there is this Bangladesh embassy and then there is this some so-called group of people, Bangladeshis, etc. but these people are extremely, uh, how to say, these are actually the bootlickers. [...] I don't want to use bad words, but these are the corrupted ones [...] morally, ethically, in all the possible ways. They are the ones who belong from the political party of this dictator [...] Before opening our mouth, it became like a habit, you know, because I would be thinking there would be an automatic signal in my brain that I have to be careful if someone is listening to me. If someone is [watching] me, you know, because that's how ... That's how bad it was. We were not allowed to speak our mind for a single second of the last 17 years of our lives. [...] And I did not want to meet this diaspora and [...] because you never know who are [regime] supporters. [WP7_13]

Therefore, security issues in the country of destination or transit concern not only state policy and the attitude of the host society but also the perception of danger stemming from the diaspora. This substantially hampers the integration process and can lead to further mobility.

Possible return or further mobility

The social attitude towards returnees was an important factor in the country of origin, potentially impacting the will to return despite security concerns. A 24-year-old man from Rwanda without documentation to stay pointed out how returnees, forced ones in particular, are treated in his country. He differentiated between perceived failure and success, the latter being the case of those who graduated in Europe. As he told us:

[B]ased on our culture, they [returnees are] just going to be classified as people who failed. [...] They'll just say you did something bad in Poland because you've been deported. So, the first thing they would just assume is that if you've been deported, it's drugs. [...] I will if I finish my studies and come back. I'll just be like, yeah, I made it. Celebrations. [WP7_3]

Something interesting was said by the Bangladeshi man quoted above, who told us that after the government change that happened in his country, he and other Bangladeshi people could consider now the possibility of returning:

I wouldn't have thought about going back to Bangladesh, to be honest, now. But now there is a possibility because we actually had a very brutal dictatorship for 17 long years and which just ended. [...] as I can see, a lot of people are actually thinking of going back, not just from, I mean, Bangladeshis who are living in Poland, but Bangladeshis who are living in, you know, abroad in various, different countries. [WP7_13]

Sometimes, the migrants were thinking about possible moves to keep the family together but, as was said by the 42-year-old woman from Dagestan, this excludes the possibility of returning to the place of origin:

It's not about the conditions, we agree to live here. If we are left together, if not, we would like to be somewhere, I don't know, together, but anywhere. I don't care. We agree to work on [such] terms; we agree to everything, but only together. This is my reason. And not Russia. [WP7_17]

She explained why she was not willing to return, pointing out the threat of conscription to the army of her sons. She said that this is possibly avoidable only through bribes, but the amount required to avoid the army constantly rises:

[T]hen they [army officials] raise the stakes. Then, they can say a year has passed, so give me more, [if you] don't give me any more, we will send your sons away. This is what they do at our house. [If] you don't give it, they simply hand over summonses, like sending your child to the army. But these children disappear after two or three months; they are brought back dead. [...] we had to leave Russia in two days, since my cousin works in the police. He said if you don't leave Russia in two days, the boys may be taken away. [...] I don't want my children to kill, for people to be killed at the hands of my children. [WP7_17]

The woman added that she is scared of being returned to her country of origin to such an extent that the threat of it would force her to move to any place from where she would not be deported to Chechnya:

If there is a threat of deportation of us and my sons, with this threat, I must go to the ends of the earth. I have to protect my children in any way. [WP7_17]

The man from Turkey currently waiting for renewal of his temporary stay permit told us that he would return if he had to help his family or take over the family business, but if he achieves his dream in Poland, he is going to stay. He also pointed out the weather when considering further mobility:

I was thinking to move [to a] Mediterranean country for [the] sea, you know, to feel like my home because I'm not used to this weather. [WP7_4]

6. Conclusion

This report presented the results on migrants' trajectories, experiences, and aspirations, with a particular focus on returns. Each story is individual and different; however, some similarities and patterns can be observed. As the collected data suggest, human agency is not determined in any simplistic way. On the one hand, it can be impacted by social structures, which can condition the decision to move, mainly if such structures endanger people's lives. They can also affect the choice of destinations if there are already established social networks acting as pull factors or if geographical or political circumstances shape the journey. On the other hand, each person perceives their level of agency in an individualised way. Some interviewees presented their stories as highly determined by external conditions, saying that they 'had to' make some kind of decision or that there were 'no other choices'. Others said they voluntarily diminished their agency, ceding the choice to fate or friends' advice. Yet, some people meticulously studied the options to select what suited them the most or put much effort and risk to reach their planned destination.

Our research was underpinned by the idea to go beyond simple categorisation of migration regarding its reasons. We strived to critically question the dichotomy of forced/voluntary migration and returns. Therefore, we decided to look at a cross-cut of categories of declared agency and plans for further mobility, independently from the reasons to be mobile. We attempted to present that both people fleeing persecution and willing to develop professionally or change their lifestyle can either retain a certain level of agency or find themselves in circumstances seriously hampering their agency. This is why we divided the findings into four categories regarding how past mobility was planned and what is the attitude towards further mobility. Among our interviewees, there was testimony fitting each category, however, not equally distributed among them.

Some people who felt highly forced to move from their country manifested much agency in choosing where to go and how to organise this journey and resist a staggering level of difficulties on the route. At the same time, people who deliberately decided to change their lives by moving somewhere else were not willing or able to select their destination, and their migration happened under the influence of others or by accident. Among both the planned and spontaneous categories of migrants there were those who wanted to settle in the place they reached, as well as those who felt more nomadic or foresee further mobility.

The possibility to judge what impacts people's will to return to their country of origin is limited. For sure, people who fled persecution or war are unwilling to return to a place where their life is endangered. However, some of them plan further mobility to other countries while

some of them want to settle in Poland. At the same time, people who meticulously planned their journey to Poland more often wanted to remain there than continue their movement. Yet, migrants who came to Poland by coincidence or due to some forces described as external to them were not more willing to move elsewhere or return to their country than to remain where they are.

The most vivid observations about the will to return or move to another destination are the following. First, an unplanned and traumatising migration experience within the EU was sometimes a factor to decide to cease movement and remain in Poland, even if it was not the initial destination. However, in the case of people forcibly returned to their origin countries, we observed problems with re-integration and the will to re-emigrate. Second, a negative attitude towards returnees in a country of origin is a serious obstacle to return. Third, secondary movements within the EU were sometimes induced by the fear of diaspora members in the case of people fleeing persecution. Fourth, the lack of a legal stay is for some an obstacle to return because they are scared that even voluntary return would result in an entry ban to the Schengen Zone in the future. Fifth, detention is not an obvious means to prevent secondary movements of asylum seekers. We talked both to people placed in open reception centres who declared their will to stay in Poland and others put in detention for whom it was such a traumatising experience that one decided to leave Poland for this reason.

The stories our interviewees shared with us also served to prepare some policy recommendations. We can offer several general recommendations to improve Poland's return system. Last but not least, our findings could contribute to further research on migrants' agency in difficult situations such as irregular stay or the experience of multiple pushbacks.

Policy recommendations

1. Ensure the possibility of restoring the deadline for submitting the application for a stay permit

Restoring the deadline for submitting any application is possible in art. 58 of the Code of Administrative Proceedings if the applicant proves that 'the infringement was without his fault'. According to § 2. of this article, 'a request to restore the deadline must be submitted within seven days from the date on which the reason for missing the deadline ceases to exist' and concomitantly 'the action for which the deadline was specified must be completed'. As some of our interviewees' stories reveal, they did not apply for renewal of their stay permit due to misinformation by private companies. These situations should be considered to prevent people who have stable lives and make integration efforts from falling into irregular stay.

2. Take into consideration an extraordinary regularising procedure

If the solution proposed in Point 1 is not possible, a special regularising option (amnesty) is advised. This procedure should be available for people who have been in Poland for a longer time and either lost their regular stay due to a difficult situation or entered Poland irregularly for an important reason, as long as they have not undertaken criminal activity and make integration efforts.

3. Reconsider the need to impose an entry ban to the Schengen Zone for returnees

As one of our interviewees declared, he would return to his country, but he is not doing so because he fears an entry ban to the Schengen Zone. Avoiding the imposition of such a ban could possibly make more irregular migrants willing to return to their countries of origin.

4. Strengthen human-rights protections and due procedures

Establish clear guidelines to prevent human-rights abuses at all stages of migration procedures, including the cessation of pushbacks. Ensure that detained migrants have access to legal representation and protection from arbitrary detention. Ensure that all the evidence presented by asylum-seekers is seriously considered during the examination of their cases.

5. Reconsider the need to apply detention in the case of asylum-seekers

Detention often can be a traumatising experience inducing secondary movement after a person is released even if he or she initially did not plan to leave Poland.

6. Design a holistic migration policy focused on integration

The new government migration strategy for 2025-2030 was adopted in October 2024 and focuses on integration processes and extending integration to labour migrants (before, it was only for beneficiaries of international protection). This is a good step that should be materialised in concrete solutions and funding.

7. Find a humanitarian solution to the crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border

The situation linked to the instrumentalisation of migration by Belarus is difficult and complex. Still, it requires solutions that guarantee the security of both migrants and Poland, as well as a stay in line with domestic, European, and international law, including the cessation of pushbacks. As our interviewees testify, the experience of migrants on this border is often extremely difficult and traumatising.

8. Promote community awareness regarding the security of migrants in Poland

As some of our interviewees declared, they decided to leave Poland irregularly (i.e., during their asylum procedure, facing the possibility of a Dublin return) due to fear of the diaspora from their country of origin. Ensuring asylum-seekers' knowledge of how Poland protects them and what measures the security services undertake to minimise the risk of infiltration of the diaspora by foreign services can lower the fear causing migrants' distress, which is often followed by secondary movement.

9. Promote community awareness regarding the situation of returnees in their countries of origin

Several of our interviewees pointed out the fear of contempt and rejection from the society of their country of origin when they returned. It would be advisable to find a way through cooperation with the countries of origin to change social perceptions of return as failure.

10. Ensure safe routes for seeking asylum in the EU

The 2024 government strategy mentions looking for new possibilities of safe routes to seek asylum in Poland. This is highly advisable as it can lower the pressure to use routes like the one through Russia and Belarus.

11. Facilitate safe return options

For those considering return, establish programmes that support safe and dignified repatriation. This should include partnerships with home countries to create reintegration programs, ensuring a smooth transition for returning migrants.

Annexes

Annex 1 - Information Letter

Research project Horizon Europe

‘GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’

Horizon Europe ‘GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’ – is the EU-funded research project (no. 101094341), led by the Uppsala University (UU) and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) in the years 2023–2026. The project focuses on the drivers of return policies and on obstacles and opportunities for international cooperation. By looking closely at governance, cooperation and actors’ behaviour, the project can suggest new avenues for international cooperation, propose recommendations for stakeholders and explore alternative routes for migrant return. The project aims to analyse governance gaps by studying diplomacy between EU Member States and third countries and by understanding migrants’ behaviour. The project conducts comparative research in 11 countries in Europe, Africa and the Middle East (including Afghanistan), in collaboration with researchers from Canada.

The Centre of Migration Research of the University of Warsaw (CMR UW) is the project partner from Poland. The CMR UW team is coordinated by dr Marta Pachocka (Principal Investigator). The Ethics Committee of the Centre of Migration Research of the University of Warsaw has approved the research application. The detailed information about the project is available on the project website: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/>. The details about the CMR team in Poland are provided at the UW website: <https://www.migracje.uw.edu.pl/projects/gaps-en/>.

We kindly ask you to agree to take part in our study to learn about your migration experiences related to your stay in Poland and with regard to (the possibility of) returning to your country. Depending on your experiences and perceptions, we focus on your plans for past and further migration. The interview focuses on the role of personal experiences in your decision-making, including your feelings and knowledge about your return, the labour market and the integration situation in your country of arrival. We are also interested in your previous attempts to return and the risks and dangers this may entail. Our questions are about the experience of return, which, depending on what you have experienced, may bring back difficult memories. We understand that it can be difficult to cope with these experiences. In this study, your safety is more important than our research interest. You may withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary and we do not pay you for it. If you agree to participate in the study, a researcher from the CMR UW project team will agree with you the details of the interview (e.g. place and time). The interview will last approximately 60-90 minutes. To avoid omitting important information from our interview, we would like to audio-

record our conversation so that we can transcribe it later. You may not agree for audio-recording. We will then take detailed notes. In all cases, we change names, locations or other specific information to ensure the anonymity of your participation.

Our research complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and national privacy and data protection laws. All information shared with us will be pseudonymised/anonymised and securely stored. Interview material will be used for research purposes in anonymised form. The results of the research will be available on the project website (www.returnmigration.eu) and through other dissemination channels.

If you have any questions about the project and participation in the study, please contact the principal investigator from CMR UW: dr Marta Pachocka, m.pachocka@uw.edu.pl.

Thank you very much for your time and interest in our project.

The GAPs team at CMR UW

Annex 2 - Interview Scenario

Note: Interviewer to fill out

Interview date:

Location:

Duration:

Language:

General identification:

Year of birth:

Nationality:

Birth place (city/country):

Sex:

Marital status:

Number of children or other dependents:

Religion and/or ethnicity:

Highest level of education:

Profession:

Current employment (if any):

Legal status: (When and how did you arrive in [current country of residence]? What is your legal status today?)

1. Integration context - livelihood and socio-cultural context

In this section of the interview, we want you to tell us how you are feeling about where you live now and what your life is like here.

1. Where do you live in this city, what is it like and do you feel at home?
2. Do you feel good with the local population? And with the country? Did that change over time? How?
3. How are you feeling about your life now? How are you feeling about being in this place? How is it compared to other places you have been to? To what extent do you feel like you belong in these different places?
4. Do you wish to stay longer in your current place? If yes, why?

2. Agency and social navigation

In this section of the interview, we want to know about your choices, goals and decisions that you have made now and in the past, both about migration to [country] and in terms of your life in general. We also want to know about your plans for the future in terms of migrating and for your life in general.

1. Please tell us how you decided where to live and where to move to. What were the reasons behind taking the decision to leave a city or country in the past?
2. What helps you to decide and what are your goals? Who do you talk to and get information or advice from? What are the main factors that you consider and why?
3. Have you looked into the possibilities of further moves? Why (yes/no)? If so, where? (third country? return?)
4. Did you contact anyone to help you to move to your current location? If yes, please describe.

3. Social networks, family and institutions

In this section of the interview, we want to know about the people—friends, family, or social groups—who are important to you, especially as they relate to the places where you have lived and you may think of living in the future.

1. What type of obligations (if any) do you have to help or care for particular relatives or friends in this country or in other countries? How does this impact your decisions on staying here or moving?
2. Are you involved in diaspora and migrant organisations? Do they help you with making decisions about migration? (if so, please explain)
3. If you have any friends, do you meet with them? How often? Do you feel support from them?

4. Changing landscapes of governance, borders and institutions

1. Would you ever go back to your country of origin? Under what conditions (if any) would you feel you could go back? If you chose to go back in the future, how would you go (i.e. land/air/sea; alone/with others)?
2. If you chose to migrate elsewhere, what are the conditions under which you would do so? If you chose to do so in the future, how would you go (i.e. land/air/sea; alone/with others; smugglers)?
3. Are you aware of any programmes or organisations that could help you to migrate onward or return? If so, what do you know about them, and how did you learn about them?
4. What are the risks and dangers of going back or leaving for another country to you personally or to members of your family?
5. What is the situation like for returnees in your country of origin? How are returnees perceived by people there? What thoughts, feelings or words come to mind when you think about returning?

Last Question: What would you recommend if you could improve your experience and situation (about return)?

Thank you!

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